

Participation and Perceptions of Citizens about Thuggery and Electoral Violence Management during 2023 General Elections in Lagos State

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Abstract

Sociopolitical conflict, thuggery and electoral violence are prevalent challenges in many developing countries, in Nigeria particularly. These are often attributed to sociopolitical factors such as marginalization, poverty, and other excruciating human conditions. This paper examines gender participation, citizen involvement, and perceptions regarding the eradication of electoral violence and thuggery, with a specific focus on Lagos State. The research adopts World Systems Theory and Social Conflict Theory particularly to elucidate the discourse. For the purpose of this study a minimum percentage of 0.0035 of the total registered voters in Lagos state (7,060,195) were sampled randomly by means of online form, amounting to approximately two hundred and forty-eight (248) completed questionnaire. Findings show that at least two in every three respondents of legal voting age in Lagos State have firsthand experience of electoral violence and thuggery. This supports assertions that violence surrounding elections is a norm in the polity, though more prevalent in the pre-election period, with 73.30% affirming, compared to a meagre 5.80% post-election.

Further, results indicate a whopping 96% agree that the male gender participates more in electoral violence and thuggery, and so equally more likely perpetrator of violence. Majority (77.40%) agree that electoral violence and thuggery can be totally eradicated in the country, while only 22.60% of respondents agree otherwise to total eradication of violence and thuggery. The study recommends electoral schooling for male citizens, improved security to curb victimization, embarking on implementation of poverty reduction policies, and promote political inclusion first to mitigate, and possibly eradicate the socio-political vices.

Keywords: Socio-political, Conflict, Thuggery, Violence, 2023 Nigerian General Elections

Introduction

Elections are very important pillars of what democracy stands for and have become the commonly accepted means of legitimating government. Once any part of the processes of an election is flawed, it becomes an invitation to anarchy and violence in the state. This may snowball into political instability (Taylor., Pevehouse, & Straus., 2017). Elections are held in

nearly all countries in the contemporary world except for a handful of states including Brunei, China, Eritrea, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and South Sudan, that are not practicing the typical Western democracy. The employment of elections to select leaders ought to provide a nonviolent alternative to the use of force, and it ought to be a mechanism that allows citizens greater say over how they are governed. Yet in practice, these expectations often fail to conform to reality. Many elections, especially those in democracies that are not yet fully consolidated, are fraught with significant levels of violence during the campaign period, on polling day or in the aftermath of voting. Electoral violence can result in casualty tolls that meet the threshold of civil war within days or weeks. When this occurs, it can undo years of peace building and development work, it can undermine democratic institutions, and it can even trigger civil war. For instance, post-election violence after the 2010 polls in Ivory Coast led to more than 1,000 civilian deaths, one million internally displaced persons and 100,000 refugees in neighbouring countries (Colombo, D'Aoust, & Sterck, 2019). Recent elections in Afghanistan, Bangladesh, India, Iraq, Kenya, Nigeria, Pakistan, and Zimbabwe were similarly accompanied by high levels of conflict. Violence, even at levels below that witnessed in the most egregious cases, undermines the democratic character of elections by substituting free choice with coercion and by deterring participation. Education, being the pillar of all developmental strides of any country is a process whereby all citizens of the state acquire skills, knowledge and attitudes to enable them to become functional members of the society. Education is seen as a key for the transformation of individual and national development. To support this assertion, Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) in her National Policy on Education states that, education in Nigeria is an instrument "par excellence" for national development. Education is designed purposely to assist individuals to develop their skills and abilities and fulfil their potential to live meaningful lives. Civic education is the near concept of education that has direct bearing with education of citizenry to become good players and law abiding in the political arena that is rounded up with conducting elections.

Elections have been held in Nigeria for over sixty years, although severally punctuated by military coups. Yet, despite its aim of allowing for peaceful transfer of power, elections held in Nigeria are known for substantial violence from the outset. When force intrudes into electoral processes, it is often indicative of weaknesses within democratic institutions and has been associated with potential disruptions to political stability and the integrity of electoral outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

No doubt, scholarship on elections in Nigeria is extensive. However, there is still gap in knowledge about level of exposure of both male and female differently to electoral thuggery and violence (Teide, 2023); the participation of same, in 2023 Nigerian general election in Lagos state, and the perception of citizens about the possibility of totally eradicating electoral thuggery and violence. This is clearly and concisely the gap this paper intends to fill.

Objectives

The study investigates citizens' experiences and perceptions of electoral violence and thuggery during the 2023 general elections in Lagos State, including an assessment of gender-related

differences in participation. To achieve this, three cognate objectives are set for the study, which are to:

1. assess the degree of exposure to electoral thuggery and violence recorded during 2023 general elections in Lagos State.
2. to assess the level of male and female participation in electoral violence and thuggery during the 2023 general elections in Lagos State.
3. Obtain views and perceptions about eradicating electoral thuggery and violence

Research Questions

This research is guided by the following questions:

1. To what extent were individuals exposed to electoral thuggery and violence during the 2023 general elections in Lagos State?
2. What were the levels of participation of male and female citizens in electoral thuggery and violence during 2023 general elections in Lagos State?
3. What did citizens view or perceive about possibility of total eradication of electoral thuggery and violence?

Conceptual Review

Conceptualization of Electoral Violence

Electoral-related violence comprises threats of coercion, physical or bodily harm and acts of intimidation perpetrated to affect or hinder an electoral process in an electoral context. When these acts are carried out, they affect the electoral process, thus may directly or indirectly influence the election process in a manner such as disruption voting pattern, and delay or derail of the outcome of the elections. Electoral violence is a form of political violence exhibited before, during and after election which often take the nature of political motivated kidnapping, killing, ballot box snatching, armed attacks on perceived opponent and the officers of electoral umpire as well as electoral stakeholders, burning of collation centers and offices for the purpose of gaining political advantage (Onimisi & Omolegbe, 2019). Pre-election violence is often more destructive in Africa, while violence on the day of election always comes in form of attacks on electoral officers, ballot snatching, voter intimidation, manipulation of electoral outcome, while violence after the election comes in form of protest, burning of facilitates and electoral materials (Straus and Taylor, 2009). Electoral violence happens in the form of arson, assassination, looting, and attacks on those involved in the electoral process such as the media, voters, politicians, destruction of electoral materials, and campaign rallies (Onapajo, 2014).

Electoral violence is a deliberate strategy used to effectively prevent opponents from voting, thereby giving the other political party a strategic advantage (Collier and Vicente, 2008). Similarly electoral violence as mental, physical structural acts targeted at blackmailing political opponent during the electoral process with the motive of shaping the electoral outcome towards a certain direction (Albert, 2007).

Thuggery and electoral violence are inflicted by political actors and/or their cronies to purposefully influence the process and outcome of elections, and it involves coercive acts against humans, property, and infrastructure (Harish and Toha, 2019). It can happen in all parts of the electoral cycle, including at the announcement of elections, party primaries, and voter registration, and it can be promoted by both state and non-state actors (Pevehouse and Straus,

2017). However, violence associated with elections can generate significant casualties and form part of an escalator process toward civil crisis. Operationally, election violence can be defined as any act of violent behaviour carried out in the way of supporting activities including pre, during and post-election periods such as use of force to disrupt political meetings and voting at polling stations, or the use of hazardous arms to threaten voters and other electoral actors, or to cause bodily damage or hurt to any human being connected with the electoral procedure. A survey of relevant datasets indicates that, a substantial proportion of elections across the globe witness at least some violence (Birch, Ursula and Höglund, 2020). The Countries at Risk of Election Violence (CREV) as the data estimated are over three quarters (78%) of elections in the countries deemed to be in risk of violence experience at ten violent events, that is while the Electoral Contention and Violence (ECAV) data report that more than three violent events in over 50% of elections had deadly violence event which is approximately 30% of elections (Daxecker, Amicarelli and Jung, 2019).

The Distinctiveness and Overview of Electoral Violence in Nigeria

The history of elections in Nigeria dates to 1922 with the introduction of Clifford Constitution. The first recorded electoral violence in post-colonial Nigeria occurred in 1964. (Adesote & Abimbola, 2014) There were also violent conflicts in parts of the Northern Region especially between supporters of the Northern People's Congress (NPC) and supporters of other parties, mainly the Northern Elements Progressive Union (NEPU) and Action Group (AG). The United Progressive Grand Alliance (UPGA) resolved to boycott the elections (Adesote & Abimbola, 2014). The Western Region became the battle ground amongst the NNDP, NPC and AG-UPGA. The upheavals led to the first military coup on January 15, 1966. This coup marked the end of the First Republic. (Oluwabiyi & Duruji, 2021).

Subsequent elections that followed were the 1979 and 1983 which ushered in Alhaji Shehu Shagari as the President in 1979 and 1983, and the legislators of the Second Republic. Again, the elections were marred by irregularities and corruption, these sparked up huge magnitude of post-election violence. With Babangida's transition programme on course, a general election was organized in 1993. The 1993 elections were believed to be the freest and fairest ever conducted in Nigeria. (Emelifeonwu, 1999) Chief M.K.O. Abiola of the Social Democratic Party was assumed to have won the election. The annulment of the election by the military junta was greeted with stiff opposition and thus, led to certain political unrest. Chief Abiola declared himself President, which further exacerbated the tension and increased instability in Nigeria till the demise of Chief M.K.O Abiola. After General Sani Abacha overthrew the Interim Government led by Chief Ernest Shonekan in 1993, he ruled until his death in 1998. Following his death, General Abdulsalami Abubakar assumed leadership and initiated a transition to civilian rule. This led to the return of Nigeria to democratic governance with the inauguration of the 4th Republic on 29th May 1999, and the swearing-in of Chief Olusegun Obasanjo as President and Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces. His government organized the 2003 election, which was marred by irregularities and conflict in almost every state of the federation. President Olusegun Obasanjo handed over power to President Umaru Musa Ya'Adua in 2007 (HRW, 2004). Upon assuming office, Ya'Adua openly acknowledged flaws in the electoral process that brought him to power. President

Jonathan organized the 2015 general election, which also, like the previous election was violence-ridden (Egobueze & Ojirika, 2017).

Good governance in Nigeria and its ability to maintain sustainability is prevented by mainly electoral violence, which takes place during most, if not all the elections. In 2007, several electoral violence Incidents took place. Approaching the 2007 elections, there were a lot of murder cases which took place (Nwolise, 2007). The 2011 general elections were better handled than the general elections that took place in 2003 and 2007, which happened under the fourth republic (Odoziobodo & Banko, 2017) However, in the 2011 elections, violence still occurred before, during and after the elections. The former President Olusegun Obasanjo did say that the elections during that period were a “do or die” situation (Bekoe, 2017). In other words, Obasanjo’s ‘do-or-die’ statement reportedly motivated both his supporters and opposition groups to engage in acts of electoral violence.

Structural Violence

Structural violence is a permanent state of violence, which is embedded in the social, political and economic structures that make up a society. Owing to the absence of concrete person and its camouflaged nature, it is also known as indirect violence. Johan Galtung describes the mechanisms, and the forms of structural violence, which are: exploitation, penetration, segmentation, marginalization, and fragmentation. (Galtung, 1990). These concepts are presented as argued by Galtung. Exploitation is based on unjust economic and social relations. It means nothing more than just a situation of ‘unequal exchange’ in which the ‘top dogs’ or the elite draw substantially more profit from the interaction taking place within this structure than the underdogs or the people excluded from development. A structure of violence not only leaves its mark on the human body but also affects the mind and the soul.

Penetration involves the implantation of agents of the powerful within the collective underdogs. In a nutshell, with the help of penetration, elements of the ‘top dog’ or elite ideology reach the consciousness of the underdog or exploited sections of society. The penetration of the ideology is linked to segmentation.

Segmentation allows the underdog only a limited view of reality. It acts to obscure the true nature of the relationship between strong and weak. The segmentation is the result of two processes, marginalization and fragmentation. Marginalization and Fragmentation exclude the peripheral agents from the center and from each other, creating greater disharmony within the periphery than within the center, while simultaneously preventing the interests of the exploited within the periphery from coinciding with the exploited within the center.

In a similar vein, Dr. Martin Luther King Jr. speaks about the Giant Triplets i.e. racism, materialism and militarism as structural forces that propagate violence or the causes of all violence (Diop, 2024). Since indirect violence is deeply rooted in pervasive societal forces, its effects are as diverse as racism, poverty, hunger, sexism, violation of human rights and militarism. Structural violence is latent as well as manifest. Moreover, it increases the latent potential for violence, such as highly tense situations which reduce individual’s capacity to pursue their objectives.

Theoretical Review

This article adopts two theories namely Social Conflict Theory as follows.

Social Conflict Theory

Social conflict theory is a Marxist-based social theory which states that social systems reflect the vested interests of those who own and control resources. The people in power use the political and economic institutions to exploit groups with less power. This causes the rest of society to become alienated or psychologically separated from the people in power. Revolutions occur to break down the social and economic separation between the people in power and the exploited people "to achieve equity and social unity".

Conflict theorists view conflicts as an engine of change, since conflict produces contradictions which are sometimes resolved, creating new conflicts and contradictions in an ongoing dialectic. In the classic example of historical materialism, Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels argue that all of human history is the result of conflict between classes, which evolved over time in accordance with changes in society's means of meeting its material needs.

Social conflict theory is a Marxist-based theory that posits that social systems reflect the vested interests of those who control resources. According to this theory, those in power use political and economic institutions to maintain dominance and exploit less powerful groups, leading to inequality and tension. This often results in alienation and unrest, with revolutions or conflict acting as catalysts for social change.

This theory is relevant to the current study because electoral thuggery and violence in Lagos State can be understood as manifestations of political conflict between dominant political elites and marginalized groups. Politicians may recruit thugs or incite violence as a strategy to maintain their power, suppress opposition, or exploit systemic weaknesses. This conflict is rooted in unequal access to political and economic resources, where the ruling elite uses violence to retain control and limit participation by those outside their circle. Marginalized groups, lacking formal power or representation, may either be co-opted into these violent networks or respond with resistance, reinforcing the cycle of instability during elections. He involvement of largely male actors in these acts of violence can also reflect deeper structural inequalities and power dynamics rooted in gender and class.

Review of Empirical Studies

Several studies have explored the dynamics of electoral violence and thuggery in Nigeria, each revealing key insights while also exposing persistent gaps in understanding the issue, particularly in terms of gender-specific involvement and citizen perceptions. For instance, Muhammad Aminu Kwasau (2022) came up with some findings namely, that thuggery has a serious negative impact on the political development of Zaria Local Government Area of Kaduna state; that the emergence of thuggery in the study area has undermined the legitimacy of the elected candidates and threatened democratic stability in Zaria Local Government Area of Kaduna state; and a lot of effort has been put in place by government through programmes and law enforcement agencies towards the control and prevention of possible future re-emergence in the study area.

In another piece on Appraisal of the 2019 Post-Electoral Violence in Nigeria, Timothy & Omolegbe (2019) opined that the 2019 general election in Nigeria witnessed one most

violence post-electoral outcome ever witnessed in the history of the democratic dispersion in the country. He identified leading causes of this violence as ethnicity and sectional in politics, in-depth ignorance, political impunity, lack of internal democracy, negative perception inflammatory campaign. Article urgent need for amendment of the electoral act thereby making provision for electronic voting system and straightening provision and enforcement of the electoral offenses section as well as re-strategized the security architecture for elections in the country.

Further, Nlemchukwu & Chioma (2019) recommended after their findings that Government agencies such as the National Orientation Agency (NOA) should be made to be functional in carrying out their responsibilities. Government can partner with the civil society in enlightening the citizenry on the need for violent free elections. The provisions of employment opportunities are highly recommended. Most people who are usually involved in electoral violence of all nature are unemployed/underemployed youths who the corrupt politicians see as the best for their bid. Unemployment renders a person hopeless and makes him a veritable and available tool for political machinations. The bill for the establishment of Electoral Offences Commission should be passed without delay. This will help in the speedy trial of electoral offenders to serve as deterrent to future violent actors.

Together, these studies offer important contributions to the discourse on electoral violence in Nigeria but leave unresolved questions. There remains a notable gap in empirical research that investigates both male and female involvement in electoral violence, alongside the lived experiences of citizens in urban political hubs such as Lagos. Even more absent is the exploration of public opinion on whether electoral violence and thuggery can ever be eradicated or what practical steps could lead to that outcome. This study responds directly to these gaps by focusing on Lagos State during the 2023 general elections, seeking to uncover the gendered dimensions of electoral violence, the nature of citizen exposure, and perceptions regarding possible solutions.

Methodology

The research is conducted largely relying on administration of a questionnaire, as well as secondary sources. For this study a minimum percentage of 0.0003 of the total registered voters in Lagos state (7,060,195) (Oguntola & Isuwa, 2023) were sampled randomly, amounting to approximately 248 (Two hundred and forty-eight) copies of a questionnaire administered either online (by means of Google forms) or physically on registered voters in the state.

The major types of data used for the study is primary data which gathered using a structured questionnaire were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The data collected for this study with the use of the instrument were distilled using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software for the processing of data, in which the data were coded into the computer. On the other hand, descriptive and inferential analyses were used for data analysis. Descriptive analysis to be adopted included the use of frequency and percentage tables, pictures, cross tabulations among others. All this was used to analyze the socioeconomic characteristics of respondents such as sex, age, marital status, educational status, occupation and monthly income distribution.

Likert scale was also used to ascertain the level of agreement to perceived causes and effects of thuggery and violence on general elections in Nigeria using Lagos as a case study.

To calculate the agreement, respondents were subjected to rate level of agreement using strongly agreed, agreed, not sure, disagree and strongly disagree.

Strongly agree takes 5, agree takes 4, not sure takes 3, disagreed is 2 and strongly disagree is 1. Each of the frequency for each satisfaction level will be used to multiply the listed number rate aforementioned.

Table 1: Description of Research Instrument(s)

S/N	Objectives	Instrument of data collection	Method of Data Analysis	Sources of Data
1	Examine the socio-economic characteristics of electoral participants.	Questionnaire	Descriptive statistics; Frequency count and percentage.	Primary
2	Examine exposure to electoral violence	Questionnaire	Descriptive statistics; Frequency count and percentage,	Primary
3	Suggestions to reduce electoral thuggery and violence.	Questionnaire	Descriptive statistics. Frequency count and percentage, and Likert scaling	Primary

Source: Authors' Work, 2023

Results and Discussion of Findings

This segment presents the result of study summarized in tabular forms and charts for easy references and analysis. It also shows answers to research questions for this research.

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondent

Table 2 presents the socio-economic characteristics.

Table 2: Socio-economic Characteristics of Respondents

Age	Below 18years	18-30 years	31-40 years	41-60 years	Above 60
	12 (4.8%)	196 (79%)	26 (10.5%)	8(3.2 %)	6 (2.4%)
Gender	Male	Female			
	142 (57.3%)	106 (42.7%)			

Source; Authors' Field Work, 20

Research Question One: How much were people exposed to electoral thuggery and violence firsthand during 2023 general elections in Lagos State?

Figure 1: Electoral Thuggery and Violence Experience

Source: Authors' Field Work, 2023

Figure 1 presents the responses of respondents when quizzed on whether they have any firsthand experience of electoral violence and thuggery with majority (69%) stating they have while only 31% said otherwise. This backs up the already established fact that violence before, during or after elections is something of a norm in the Nigerian political sphere. According to this statistics it is correct to say at least two (2) in every three (3) Nigerians in Lagos State and of legal voting age have firsthand experience electoral violence and thuggery.

Figure 2: Period of Violence

Source: Authors' Field Work, 2023

Figure 2 shows the result when 69% of respondents who agreed to have firsthand experience of electoral violence were further asked to state what period of elections did they experience

such. 73.30% said pre-election period, 20.90% during election with a meagre 5.80% stating it was after election.

This is insinuating that in Lagos state, violence during the campaign period between opposing political parties and thugs is quite more rampant than violence during and after elections combined. However, violence during and after election both seem to receive more public and media attention than during the campaign period ranging from assassinations of aspirants, vandalization of campaign posters and finally attack on members on campaign rallies.

Research Question Two: What were the levels of participation of male and female citizens in thuggery and violence during 2023 general elections in Lagos State?

Figure 3: Gender Participation in Electoral Thuggery and Violence
Source; Authors' Field Work, 2023

The information presented in figure 3 shows the opinion of respondents on the gender that participates most in electoral violence and thuggery. A whopping 96% agreed that the male gender participates most in electoral violence and thuggery as compared to 4% who agreed that it is the female gender. This supports the notion that, within the context of electoral violence and related aggression, males are more frequently identified as perpetrators and are statistically more likely to injure, harm, others, particularly in patriarchal societies where aggression is often gendered.

Research Question Three: What did citizens view or perceive about possibility of total eradication of electoral thuggery and violence? In order to answer this research question, respondents were required to decide in a two-boundary alternatives, as to whether or not electoral violence can be eradicated absolutely. An overwhelming majority of responses are positive about eradication. The responses are represented as follows.

Figure 5: Eradication of Electoral Violence

Source; Authors’ Field Work, 2023

Figure 5 presents the responses of respondents on their opinion about the total eradication of violence and thuggery. Majority (77.40%) agree that electoral violence and thuggery can be totally eradicated in the country while only 22.60% of respondents agreed otherwise probably due to the rumored talk that Nigerians are generally stubborn.

Table 3 presents respondents’ choices from a list of suggested measures provided in the questionnaire regarding how electoral violence and thuggery could be eradicated. Improved or enhanced security, reduced corruption, better governance, enhanced orientation or education, improved unity, stricter punishments for offenders, reduction of poverty and improved employment where the most cited suggestions towards the said phenomenon of this study with each of the aforementioned suggestions taking 30%, 15%, 7%, 10%, 4%, 18%, 11% and 5% percent respectively.

Table 3: Suggestions toward Eradication of Electoral Violence and Thuggery

Suggestions	Percentage (%)
<i>Improved/enhanced security</i>	<i>30</i>
<i>Reduced corruption</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>Better governance</i>	<i>7</i>
<i>Enhanced orientation/education</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>Improved unity</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>Stricter punishments for offenders</i>	<i>18</i>
<i>Reduction of poverty</i>	<i>11</i>
<i>Improved employment</i>	<i>5</i>

Source; Authors’ Field Work, 2023

Discussion

This study highlights the entrenched nature of electoral violence in Lagos State, particularly during the 2023 general elections. The fact that 69% of respondents reported firsthand experience of electoral violence reinforces longstanding arguments that violence is a systemic feature of Nigeria's electoral process. According to Muhammed (2014), electoral violence in Nigeria is often structurally embedded, driven by political elites who weaponize thuggery to gain power. This high prevalence not only disrupts democratic participation but also reflects critical lapses in election security and institutional accountability.

Of particular concern is the finding that 73.3% of electoral violence occurred during the pre-election period. This aligns with Bekoe's (2012) assertion that pre-election violence is a strategic tool used by political actors to shape electoral outcomes in their favor—through voter intimidation, destruction of campaign infrastructure, and suppression of opposition mobilization. In Lagos, this trend suggests that violence is used not only to disrupt voting but to actively shape the political field long before election day. It highlights a pressing need for electoral stakeholders to shift attention and resources to the pre-election phase in both monitoring and security deployment.

The gendered dimension of the findings also reveals troubling patterns. A striking 96% of respondents identified men as the primary perpetrators of electoral violence, a result that reflects broader patterns of political violence being male dominated. Tripp (2016) explains that electoral violence tends to reinforce patriarchal structures, often deterring women from participating in political processes through both physical and psychological intimidation. In Lagos, this dynamic contributes to the systemic marginalization of women in politics by creating an environment of fear and physical insecurity that discourages female participation. The threat or actual use of violence, often perpetrated by male political actors or thugs, deters women from contesting for political office, attending rallies, or even voting. Additionally, cultural expectations around female respectability and safety further restrict women's visibility in public political spaces, reinforcing gendered power imbalances and limiting their influence in the democratic process.

Despite the widespread nature of violence, it is notable that 77.4% of respondents believe electoral violence can be completely eradicated. This optimism suggests a strong public desire for reform and institutional transformation. Respondents' proposed solutions—enhanced security, reduced corruption, better governance, and improved civic education—echo policy recommendations from electoral bodies and development partners. Enhanced security would deter the activities of political thugs and provide citizens with a safer environment to participate in elections. Reducing corruption addresses the root causes of political desperation and manipulation that often lead to violence. Improved governance builds public trust and reduces the likelihood of citizens resorting to violence to express dissatisfaction.

In sum, the findings of this study contribute to the growing discourse on electoral governance and democratic development in Nigeria. Enabled by weak institutional enforcement, electoral violence and thuggery remain an issue, but the belief in the possibility of reform offers a promising future especially in terms of policy interventions.

Conclusion

Political violence manifest in acrimony, assault, assassination, intimidation, harassment, maiming and killing consequently these affect the existing social relationship in the society. This paper has attempted to discuss the degree of exposure of male and female gender to electoral thuggery and violence recorded during 2023 general elections, determine participation in thuggery and violence in Lagos State, and get perceptions of citizens about eradicating electoral thuggery and violence of political violence in Nigeria. The findings revealed that while both genders were affected, males were more likely to be involved as perpetrators, particularly during the pre-election period. Moreover, citizens expressed a strong desire for systemic reforms and stricter enforcement to curb such violence. By examining these gendered patterns and public perceptions, the study emphasizes the need for inclusive and preventive solutions that electoral violence and promoting healthier political engagement in Nigeria.

Recommendations

In line with the tripod objectives of the paper and findings thereof, three recommendations are offered.

First, on the basis of prevalence of violence pre-election period, the study recommends electoral schooling for male citizens, more likely perpetrator of violence and are significantly more likely to suffer worse outcomes.

Second, in order to deal with participation in electoral violence and thuggery, improved security to curb victimization, embarking on implementation of poverty reduction policies, and promote political inclusion to mitigate first to mitigate, and possibly eradicate the sociopolitical vices.

Third, improved security ranks foremost among measures for dealing with violence and thuggery, as eradication of vices is somewhat unattainable, despite research results showing overwhelming acceptance of eradication possibility.

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